

Supplemental material for:

Multiple routes to color convergence in a radiation of Neotropical poison frogs

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pigment Analyses

After measuring skin reflectance, frogs were euthanized with a lidocaine injection and skinned. All further procedures were done in darkness under the red light of a Petzl Tikka XP headlamp. Skins were either processed immediately for absorbance spectrometry or dried onto mirror glass for preservation for TLC. For absorbance, skins were split by body region, dried slightly, and placed into 500 μ l chloroform for 2 hr to extract carotenoids. Skins were then transferred to 500 μ l of 70% ethanol with 3% ammonium hydroxide for 2 hr to extract pterins. Immediately after extraction, we measured UV-VIS-NIR absorbance in a 400- μ l quartz cuvette relative to a blank containing the extraction solvent.

Pigment concentrations were determined from absorbance spectra using the Beer-Lambert law (Hudon and Brush 1992):

$$A \times \text{volume of extract} (\mu\text{l}) \times 10^4 \left[E_{1\text{cm}}^{1\%} \times \text{skin area} (\text{cm}^2) \right]$$

where A is the absorbance and $E_{1\text{cm}}^{1\%}$ is the extinction coefficient for that particular pigment. For carotenoid extracts, A was defined as the absorbance maximum of the spectrum minus absorbance at 600 nm (serving as a baseline) and $E_{1\text{cm}}^{1\%}$ was set to 2500 (Hudon and Brush 1992). For pterin extracts, A was defined as the absorbance at 500 nm, corresponding to the peak absorbance wavelength of drosopterin, a red pterin pigment commonly found in amphibians (Obika and Bagnara 1964). Thus, this “pterin” concentration does not measure the concentration of colorless pterins but instead corresponds to drosopterin concentration. As with the carotenoid extracts, we subtracted absorbance at 600 nm from this value to serve as a baseline read, and $E_{1\text{cm}}^{1\%}$ was set to 680 (Weiss et al. 2012). Skin area was calculated from standardized dorsal photos by taking pixel counts of colored areas of the dorsum and converting to cm^2 from a standardized reference measurement included with each photo.

For TLC, carotenoids were extracted from dried skins by soaking the tissue for 2 hr in 200 μ l 1:1 hexane:MTBE stabilized with 0.1% BHT. This extract was removed, and the tissue was soaked with an additional 50 μ l extraction solvent for 15 min to ensure complete carotenoid extraction. These two extracts were combined, dried down to approximately 20 μ l, and spotted into the corner of 10 cm X 10 cm X 0.1 cm silica TLC plates. Ascending TLC was conducted in three steps, first with 10 ml of a 7:3 ratio of hexane to acetone for 6 cm, then with 10 ml of a 95:5 ratio of hexane to acetone for 9 cm in the same direction, and finally with a 6:4 ratio of hexane to ethyl acetate for 9 cm perpendicular to the first two developments. Plates were photographed after each development for calculation of retention factor (Rf) values. After the final development, spots were

scraped and eluted with 30–200 μl ethanol, and absorbance spectra were recorded in a 10- μl minimum-capacity quartz cuvette. Carotenoid identifications followed Twomey et al. (2020b, 2020a).

Pterins were extracted from the carotenoid-stripped skins with 200 μl of 70% ethanol with 3% ammonium hydroxide for 2 hr. Skins were then removed, and 600 μl of chloroform was added to the extract and mixed. The sample was centrifuged at 13,200 RPM for 10 minutes, resulting in the formation of an upper layer which was highly fluorescent under UV illumination (Frost and Robinson 1984). This upper layer, which contained pterins, was drawn off and evaporated to dryness with a Speedvac. For TLC, the dried pterin extract was resuspended with 40 μl extraction solvent; half of this was spotted onto a silica-cellulose TLC plate (0.25 mm thick, 10 \times 10 cm). Ascending TLC was done in two dimensions, first with 14 ml propanol/7 ml 7% ammonium hydroxide as a mobile phase, second with 10 ml butanol/3.5 ml water/1.5 ml glacial acetic acid as a mobile phase. Plates were photographed under a standard black light ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 366 \text{ nm}$), which causes pterins to fluoresce. Drosopterin could be detected by its low R_f value in both mobile phases combined with its diagnostic reddish-orange fluorescence under black light.

RGB Rendering and Dorsal Color Ancestral State Reconstruction

For visual representation on the phylogeny, frog dorsal color was rendered into RGB values (Fig. 1) with the color picker tool (10 pixel radius) in GIMP version 2.10 using dorsal photos of frogs against a white piece of paper. Using this tool, we extracted the RGB values from six points on the brightly colored parts of the dorsum. RGB values were normalized to a maximum of 255 to facilitate visual interpretation and averaged per individual.

Mapping dorsal color onto the phylogeny posed a challenge as it requires the simultaneous mapping and rendering of three separate continuous variables (in the case of RGB colorspace) corresponding to each color channel. To solve this problem, we mapped dorsal RGB values separately by color channel, resulting in three different “color trees”, each using a color ramp extending from 0 (black) to 255 for that particular color (e.g., the “blue” tree used a black-to-blue ramp with limits 0 and 255). These three trees were then blended in Inkscape version 0.92.5 using filters set to “Screen” mode, which blended the three overlaid trees to an accurate RGB representation (Fig. 1). We could verify that the colors were blended correctly as the colors rendered at the tips of the phylogeny were identical to the observed RGB values. We note that this procedure was done simply as a way to visually represent “color” as a continuous trait that could be displayed on a phylogeny; comparative analyses of dorsal color evolution were based on the reflectance spectrum-derived color metric described in the main text (see also Figure 2b).

Pigment absorbance spectra were rendered into RGB for display as follows. First, for a given sample, the raw absorbance spectrum was adjusted by:

$$A_{adj}(\lambda) = (A(\lambda) - A_{600}) \times 0.3 / \text{skin area} (\text{cm}^2)$$

where $A(\lambda)$ is the raw absorbance at wavelength λ , A_{600} is the raw absorbance at 600 nm, serving as a baseline read, 0.3 is a constant (equivalent to the concentration coefficient of the pigment sensu Grether et al. 2004), and skin area as defined above. Using this adjusted absorbance spectrum, reflectance was then modeled using a simplification of a model for calculating reflectance from Grether et al. (2004). First, transmission through the pigment layer is calculated from:

$$T_1(\lambda) = 10^{-A_{adj}(\lambda)}$$

where $T_1(\lambda)$ is the proportion of transmitted light at wavelength λ and $A_{adj}(\lambda)$ is the adjusted absorbance value at wavelength λ , as defined above. Overall reflectance can be calculated from:

$$T_1(\lambda)^2 R_2(\lambda)$$

where $R_2(\lambda)$ is the reflectance at wavelength λ . For simplicity, we modeled pigment color on a white background with 100% reflectance at every wavelength ($R_2(\lambda) = 1$), therefore, this equation can be simplified to $T_1(\lambda)^2$. We then used the *spec2rgb* function of Pavo2 (Maia et al. 2019) to render this spectrum into RGB values used for depicting the colors of extracted pigments on Fig. 1.

Sequencing Read Cleaning, Assembly, and UCE Alignment

Reads were quality-trimmed with Trimmomatic version 0.38 (Bolger et al. 2014), with the following parameters: paired-end mode, ILLUMINACLIP:2:30:10, LEADING:5, TRAILING:15, SLIDINGWINDOW:4:15, MINLEN:40, using the *illumiprocessor* command of phyluce. Reads were assembled into contigs with SPAdes version 3.12 (Bankevich et al. 2012) run in paired-end mode with three kmer lengths (21, 33, 53) and coverage cutoff = 5, using the *phyluce_assembly_assembly_spades* command. We then used the standard phyluce workflow to identify UCE loci among the contigs and write these UCE loci to fasta files. Locus alignments were done with MAFFT version 7.130b (Katoh and Standley 2013) using the *phyluce_align_seqcap_align* command, and internally trimmed with Gblocks version 0.91b (Castresana 2000) using the *phyluce_align_get_gblocks_trimmed_alignments_from_untrimmed* command.

RESULTS

Additional Carotenoids and Pterins

Canary xanthophylls, which are most likely metabolic derivatives of lutein, were found only in *R. imitator* and *R. sirensis* (Fig. S4). Character mapping indicates that the most likely scenario involves absence at the root (posterior probability = 0.71), followed by a single gain ($\bar{x} = 1.3 \pm 0.03$), most likely at the base of the *vanzolinii* clade, and single loss ($\bar{x} = 1.0 \pm 0.03$) in the *flavovittata* clade, although the alternative scenario of two independent gains in *R. sirensis* and *R. imitator* is nearly as likely (Fig. S4). Aside from the C-4 ketocarotenoids found in *R. sirensis* and *R. summersi*, an additional red carotenoid (“eschscholtzanthin-like”), previously known from the banded morph of *R. imitator* (Twomey et al. 2020b) and red *R. sirensis* (Twomey et al. 2020a), was not detected in any other species. Our analyses indicate absence at the root (posterior probability = 0.96), two independent gains ($\bar{x} = 2.1 \pm 0.01$) within the *vanzolinii* clade, and no losses ($\bar{x} = 0.4 \pm 0.02$) (Fig. S4).

We found that drosopterin-containing species typically also had sepiapterin, a yellow pterin pigment. We detected sepiapterin in *Ranitomeya amazonica*, *R. reticulata*, and *R. benedicta*; previously it was also detected in *R. fantastica*, *R. summersi*, and *R. imitator* (Twomey et al. 2020b). Discrete character mapping of sepiapterin is shown in Figure S6. We noted that, when TLC plates were viewed under visible light, whereas drosopterin and carotenoids were easily visible on the plate as colored spots, sepiapterin was not, suggesting that it is likely at low enough concentrations to have little or no contribution to the color of these frogs. TLC analyses of pterin extracts further revealed the presence of a large number of colorless, UV-absorbing pterins. These pterins fluoresce blue, green, or violet under UV light and are invisible under standard room

lighting. For the purposes of the current study, we do not discuss these colorless pterins further as they probably contribute only weakly or not at all to frog color (but see Oliphant and Hudon (1993) and Wagner et al. (2021) for possible roles of colorless pterins in color production).

Supplemental figures

A) *vanzolinii* clade

B) *fantastica* clade

Figure S1. Absorbance spectra of pigment extracts from *Ranitomeya*. (A) *vanzolinii* clade, (B) *fantastica* clade. Blue lines are absorbance of the ammonia extract, which contains pterins; red lines are absorbance of the chloroform extract, which contains carotenoids. Solid lines indicate mean; shaded areas indicate standard deviation. Numbers above spectra indicate the wavelength of peak absorbance of pterins and carotenoids.

Figure S2. Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of *Ranitomeya* and outgroups, using 49 separate partitions for models of DNA evolution. Numbers at internal nodes represent percentage of ultrafast bootstrap and gene and site concordance factors, respectively. Asterisks indicate 100% bootstrap support. Information on sample origin is given in Table S2.

Figure S3. Results from the phylogenetic Monte Carlo procedure (PMC), testing the fits of all three evolutionary models (white noise, BM, and OU) for four continuous traits. Briefly, this method calculates the likelihood ratio δ as twice the difference in log likelihood of observing the data under two competing models. Distributions of δ under model 1 (pink shaded area) and model 0 (blue shaded area) are calculated from a Monte Carlo procedure. The dotted line indicates the observed value of δ when the model was fit to that trait. For the dorsal color metric and pterin concentration, white noise is strongly rejected, while BM and OU had similar support (with AICc slightly favoring BM in both cases; Table S3). For both carotenoid concentration and reflectance λ_{max} , OU was somewhat more plausible than white noise, with BM somewhat strongly rejected in both cases.

Figure S4. Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of *Ranitomeya* and outgroups, using a single partition and hence single model of DNA evolution. Numbers at internal nodes represent ultrafast bootstrap percentages.

Figure S5. Pigment concentrations in *Ranitomeya*. These values are derived from pigment absorbance spectra (Fig. 2). For carotenoids, concentrations were calculated from the maximum absorbance. For pterins, concentrations were calculated from the absorbance at 500 nm which is the absorbance maximum for drosopterin. Bars indicate mean and dots indicate individual samples. The rectangle to the right of each name shows the RGB dorsal color of that taxon.

Figure S6. Ancestral state reconstructions for presence/absence of additional carotenoid and pterin pigments in *Ranitomeya*. Pigments were scored as present/absent based on TLC results and absorbance spectra. Pigment color (red/yellow) is indicated with the label color. Observed states are shown at the tips; pie charts at internal nodes represent posterior probabilities of each state. Boxes report the mean \pm standard error for the numbers of total changes, gains, and losses calculated from the 1000 stochastic mapping iterations.

Legends for supplemental tables

Table S1. Sampling localities, sample sizes, and data sources for skin pigment and reflectance dataset.

Table S2. Sampling localities, voucher codes, and data sources for samples included in the phylogenetic analysis. Museum acronyms: **MNCN:** Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain; **MCP:** Museu de Ciências e Tecnologia, Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, Brazil.

Table S3. Model fitting results. For each continuous trait, three models were fit and ranked according to their AICc.

Table S4. Partition scheme for phylogenetic analysis. For each of 49 models of DNA evolution, the UCE loci analyzed under the corresponding model are listed.

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